

Review

Recent applications and novel strategies for mercury determination in environmental samples using microextraction-based approaches: A review

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Strategies for environmental Hg determination using microextraction-based approaches were reviewed.
- The developed methods comply with the principles of green analytical chemistry.
- The approaches discussed are mostly based on the use of new materials and analytical procedures.
- The use of sustainable materials, in-situ sampling, and optimization by experimental design remain to be improved.
- Metrological support in method and technology development is urgently needed to get comparable and SI-traceable data.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Abbreviations: DVB/CAR/PDMS, Divinyl-benzene/Carboxen/Polydimethylsiloxane; CPE, Cloud Point Extraction; CV-AAS, Cold Vapor-Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry; CV-AFS, Cold Vapor-Atomic Fluorescence Spectrophotometry; CD-IMS, Corona Discharge ionization Ion Mobility Spectrometry; DLLME, Dispersive Liquid-Liquid Microextraction; DLLME-SFO, Dispersive Liquid-Liquid Microextraction based on the Solidification of Floating Organic drop; D-DLLME, Displacement Dispersive Liquid-Liquid Microextraction; dHS-ITEX, Dynamic Headspace In-Tube Extraction; DPSV, Differential Pulse Stripping Voltammetry; d-CPE, dual Cloud Point Extraction; d- μ SPE, Dispersive micro Solid Phase Extraction; EME, Electromembrane Extraction; ETAAS, Electrothermal Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry; EW-LLME, Exchangeable Water- Liquid Liquid Microextraction; FD, Fluorescence Detection; FI-MSPME, Flow Injection Magnetic Solid Phase Microextraction; GC, Gas chromatography; GC-OBD-OES, Gas Chromatography Dielectric Barrier Discharge Optical Emission Spectrometry; GC-Py-AFS, Gas Chromatography Atomic Fluorescence Spectrophotometry via a Pyrolytic reactor; GFAAS, Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry; HF-LPME, Hollow Fiber Liquid Phase Microextraction; HG-AFS, Hydride Generation Atomic Fluorescence Spectrophotometry; HS-SPME, Headspace Solid Phase Microextraction; HR-CS ETAAS, High-Resolution Continuum Source Electrothermal Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry; ISLD-DLLME, In Syringe Low Density Solvent-Dispersive Liquid Liquid Microextraction; IT-SPME, In-Tube Solid Phase Microextraction; LOD, Limit of Detection; LPME, Liquid Phase Microextraction; LLE, Liquid Liquid Extraction; MIP-OES, Microwave Induced Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry; PCVG, Photochemical Vapor Generation; PDMS, Polydimethylsiloxane; DVB/PMDS, Divinyl-benzene/Polydimethylsiloxane; PD-OES, Microplasma Point Discharge Optical Emission Spectrometry; SFODME, Solidified Floating Organic Drop Microextraction; SPS-LPME, Switchable-Polarity Solvent Liquid Phase Microextraction; SS-DLPME, Syringe-to-Syringe Dispersive Liquid-Phase Microextraction; SUPRAS-UA-HLLME, SUPRAMolecular Solvent based Ultrasound-Assisted Homogeneous Liquid Liquid Microextraction; SPCnAuEs, Screen-Printed Carbon Electrodes modified with gold nanoparticles; SPE, Solid Phase Extraction; SWASV, Square Wave Anodic Stripping Voltammetry; μ SPE, micro Solid Phase Extraction; SPME, Solid Phase Microextraction; TD-AAS, Thermal Decomposition- Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry; TXRF, X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometry; UA-CPE, Ultrasound Assisted Cloud Point Extraction; USAEME, Ultrasound Assisted Emulsification Microextraction; USA DMSPE, Ultrasound Assisted Dispersive Micro Solid-Phase Extraction.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.128823>

Received 23 December 2021; Received in revised form 25 March 2022; Accepted 29 March 2022

Available online 1 April 2022

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ARTICLE INFO

Editor: John D Atkinson

Keywords:

Mercury determination
Microextraction techniques
Environmental monitoring
Exposomics studies
Green analytical chemistry (GAC)
Sample preparation

ABSTRACT

The growing need to monitor Hg levels in the environment to control its emissions and evaluate the effectiveness of reduction policies is driving the scientific community to focus efforts on creating analytical methods that are simpler, lower cost, more performing, and environmentally sustainable. In this context, an important contribution is provided by microextraction techniques, which have long proven to be simple, reliable, and to ensure an environmentally responsible sample preparation. This manuscript reviews the recent progress in the determination of environmental Hg using microextraction techniques. The considered studies involve all environmental compartments (i.e., air, water, soil, and biota) and have been discussed by grouping them according to the employed technique while pointing out the main advances achieved and the most important limitations. The ultimate goal is to provide an up-to-date overview of the analytical potential of microextraction techniques that can be exploited in various investigation fields and to highlight the most important knowledge gaps that should be addressed in the coming years, such as in-situ sampling, the use of natural materials, and the value of metrological support to obtain data SI-traceable and comparable.

1. Introduction

The intensification of anthropogenic activities in recent decades has resulted in an overall increase in environmental pollution due to the presence of metals and organometallic compounds. In this context, Hg is of particular relevance because of its high mobility and residence time in the environment, with the result that it is a pervasive and ubiquitous pollutant (UNEP, 2013). Hg is a toxic element due to the neurological and behavioral disorders that produce after inhalation, ingestion, or dermal exposure that can lead to the onset of symptoms such as numbness in the hands and feet, hearing damage, difficulty articulating words, and even death (UNEP, 2013; WHO, 2017). Therefore, Hg has been included by the World Health Organization (WHO) in the list of the 10 most toxic chemicals or groups of chemicals (WHO, 2017), and the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) of the United States (US) has placed Hg third on its list of the most hazardous substances (ATSDR, 2019).

Hg can be emitted from natural sources, including volcanic eruptions and wildfires, but also from anthropogenic sources, such as waste incineration and emissions from fossil fuel combustion processes for energy production (UNEP, 2019a). Since the tragic incident that occurred in Minamata Bay in 1953, Hg has taken on an increasingly prominent role as a global pollutant, and nowadays it is the target of several international research programs and projects (e.g., “ERA PLANET”, “GMOS”, “GMOS TRAIN”, “GOS4M”) aiming at a more accurate knowledge of its current impact, spatial patterns, temporal trends, and future scenarios (ERA PLANET; GMOS; GMOS TRAIN; GOS4M). Synergistically, other projects have been working on the metrological side of Hg monitoring trying to improve the accuracy and the confidence in the measurements through the development of SI-traceable protocols and devices (e.g., “MercOx”, “SI-Hg”) (MercOx; SI-Hg). These results are also being achieved through the implementation of monitoring networks in support of the objectives of the Minamata Convention on Mercury (MCM), whose goals include the control of Hg exposure and the reduction of its use and emissions (UNEP, 2019b).

Owing to its chemical-physical properties, Hg is present in the environment in various species with different toxicity. It follows that the determination of the total concentration of Hg (THg) alone is not sufficient to define the severity of contamination, and its speciation is essential to accurately assess the extent of exposure. Hg is present in the environment as an elemental species (Hg^0), or as a cationic inorganic species (iHg) in the + 1 or + 2 oxidation state. It also produces organometallic compounds, which are more toxic than the inorganic species, and in particular methylmercury is well known for its ability to accumulate in the tissues of organisms and biomagnify through the food chain (Clarkson and Magos, 2006).

Given its hazardousness even at low concentrations, threshold values for Hg have been provided by international public health organizations and implemented at the national level by policy and surveillance

agencies. For instance, the WHO has set a value of 6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ (for a 60-Kg adult drinking 2 liters of water per day) as an acceptable threshold for THg in drinking water (WHO, 2005). In Europe a legal limit of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ was set in the Directive (EU) 2020/2184 on the quality of water intended for human consumption, while the EPA has established a threshold of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ for Hg in drinking water (www.wqa.org). Concentration thresholds have also been established for ambient air, where this limit is 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, as estimated in the WHO guidelines (WHO, 2000), whereas for residential soils, the UK Environment Agency, indicated values of 1 mg/Kg, 170 mg/Kg, and 11 mg/Kg of dry weight for elemental, inorganic, and methylmercury, respectively (Morgan Hannah et al., 2004). As for the biota, the European Union set at 20 ng/g THg the Environmental Quality Standard (EQS) for piscivore wildlife (proposal COM 2011/876 amending Directive 2008/105/EC). Hence, strict Hg monitoring in various environmental media is essential to assess its potential impact on human health and wildlife, and its outcomes are of interest not only to academics but also to numerous policymakers and stakeholders. Indeed, the MCM requires the parties to adopt appropriate mechanisms to monitor the effectiveness of the convention (article 22) and encourages the scientific community to invest resources in the advancement of investigation methods (article 19) to improve the assessment of Hg levels (UNEP, 2019b). This knowledge is the most effective tool to make strategic actions to reduce Hg levels globally, but it also supports studies in other scientific fields such as external exposure assessment and envirometallomics (Chen et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021).

Hg distribution among the various environmental compartments is complex, as well as its chemical behavior. Therefore, the assessment of Hg exposure levels needs to be approached as comprehensively as possible with special attention to air and biota (UNEP, 2021). Indeed, measuring Hg concentrations in biota is a key point for assessing ecosystem pollution, while air is the environmental compartment primarily linked to important natural and anthropogenic emission sources where Hg species exist with different residence times, which facilitate the distribution of this pollutant even over long distances (UNEP, 2021). Therefore, investigation of Hg levels also in pristine areas is fundamental for large-scale monitoring (Moretti et al., 2021, 2020), which can also be carried out by strategies that exploit passive sampling for the Hg quantification in poorly accessible sites (Naccarato et al., 2020b).

From an analytical standpoint, the Hg presence in trace amounts implicates a thorough sample preparation which often includes a pre-concentration, also due to the frequent co-presence in the matrix of other metal ions that may interfere in the analytical determination (Shi et al., 2019). This crucial step of the analytical workflow can be challenging, and often requires the simultaneous evaluation of several parameters (Naccarato et al., 2018a). Furthermore, in a perspective of collaboration at the international level between scientific research and political strategies, new methods and/or techniques for Hg determination cannot prevent taking seriously into account that the measurements

produced are metrologically comparable and open to the public.

In past decades, sample-prep procedures used in Hg determination have included liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) (Chromatography and Ultraviolet, 1992) and solid-phase extraction (SPE) (Escudero et al., 2013; Rajesh and Gurulakshmanan, 2008; US-EPA, 2014), frequently engaging the use of cysteine, thiosulfates, or other reagents containing thiol groups in the extraction process to promote phase transfer (Leermakers et al., 2005). The Hg determination in environmental matrices can currently be carried out in compliance with methods proposed by international bodies such as the US-Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) (e.g., method IO-5 for vapor and particle-phase, EPA 1631e and CEN EN 13506:2001 for aqueous matrices, EPA 7473 for Hg in solids and solutions, UNI EN 15852 for gaseous Hg in ambient air), which involve the quantification by Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) or spectrophotometric techniques that usually entail a red-ox reaction of Hg in the sample preparation with the resulting production of large quantities of waste for disposal (Naccarato et al., 2020a; Tassone et al., 2020).

Although these protocols are reliable, their development did not account for the environmental impact of the extensive use. In recent years, the emergence of new methods with a low ecological footprint, rapid, and automated has been also involving Hg quantification in the different environmental compartments. Nowadays, the analytical techniques that can provide advantages in this direction are numerous, and among these an important role is certainly covered by the broad family of microextraction techniques in which, by definition, the extractive phase is reduced compared to the albeit limited required sample volume (Naccarato and Tagarelli, 2019). Some of these techniques are now well-established, commercially available, and have permitted the outcome of cost-effective and reliable high-throughput methods for the determination of trace analytes even in highly complex matrices (Naccarato et al., 2021, 2018b).

The purpose of this review is to provide an overview of the state-of-the-art in the application and development of microextraction techniques, for the determination of Hg and its compounds in environmental matrices, highlighting how the evolution of these techniques is also effective in this field of investigation. The studies herein reviewed, which do not include the use of sensor devices, were published during the past 8 years (2014–2021) in the leading journals indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, therefore the manuscript is intended to be an update of the last review published in 2014 (Rutkowska et al., 2014). The papers were reviewed by grouping them according to the microextraction technique used and the nature of the extracting phase, i.e., solid-phase sorbents (Table 1) or liquid-phase solvents (Table 2). In the discussion, the key working principles of the techniques were recalled (Table 3) and the studies were compared showing their main results in terms of analytical performance and environmental impact, but also their limits, the challenges, and the future outlook in the research field.

2. Microextraction techniques based on solid extraction phases

2.1. Micro-solid phase extraction

In recent years, the need to develop green methods has led research to improve miniaturized SPE techniques such as micro-solid phase extraction (μ -SPE), which permit the work of small amounts of sample, with lower consumption of solvent and waste products, while maintaining the performance of the classic SPE (Table 3). The most innovative applications for Hg determination by μ -SPE in environmental matrices have been realized through the development of new sorbent materials, including activated carbon xerogel (Carrera et al., 2016), magnetic particles functionalized with silver nanoparticles (López-García et al., 2015), and using spectrophotometric techniques for Hg detection, which are considered green for the low-energy demand and low-waste generation. Although these are not top-performing

analytical instrumentations, the recent methods in which they were involved achieved high sensitivity owing to the combination with a sample preparation based on μ -SPE with the use of novel hybrid sorption nanomaterials, such as those based on graphene oxide functionalized with ILs, and 3D graphene-Ni foam functionalized with ILs. These protocols also permitted the determination of Hg^{2+} , MeHg^+ , and PhHg^+ without the need for chromatographic systems, and the synthesized hybrid nanomaterial allowed up to 250 extraction cycles (Sotolongo et al., 2020, 2018).

Potentially higher extraction efficiencies can be achieved with the use of d- μ SPE, where the Hg sorption kinetics is improved by dispersing the solid sorbent in the aqueous sample. In this regard, Krawczyk and Stanisiz (Krawczyk and Stanisiz, 2015) applied for the first time the ultrasound-assisted d- μ SPE for the determination of Hg^{2+} in water samples using a solid sorbent with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) that were dissolved by strong acids, therefore preventing their reusability.

More straightforward sorbent recoveries were accomplished through the use of materials with magnetic properties such as graphitic carbon nitride ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$) (Shi et al., 2019), thiosemicarbazide-functionalized carbon nanotubes (CNT-TSC) (Musielak et al., 2021), doped silica gel magnetic nanoparticles (ODE@ SiO_2 @MNP) (Khor et al., 2019), dendrimer functionalized magnetic nano sorbent (Ghodsi et al., 2021), and dispersing magnetic graphene in a 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium ionic liquid [Hmim] (Faryadras et al., 2020). Following this strategy, the separation of the sorbent was made possible by the application of a magnetic field, resulting in simple and effective methods.

2.2. In-fiber solid-phase microextraction

Particularly effective from an environmental perspective is solid-phase microextraction (SPME), an established analytical technique that integrates solventless extraction and pre-concentration of analytes in a single step (Elliani et al., 2020). SPME is to be considered the forefather and founder technique of the "microextraction family" whose introduction in the early 1990s has certainly inspired and oriented the analytical chemistry of the following decades. In particular, SPME in headspace mode (HS-SPME) is preferred in the case of complex matrices because it allows for the extraction of target compounds from the sample headspace while solving problems related to matrix effects, minimizing analyte drag, and also increasing fiber lifetime. In Hg determination, however, a derivatization step is required before extraction due to the low volatility of the compounds to be analyzed (Li et al., 2020). This reaction has mostly been carried out with the use of borate compounds that perform a rapid alkylation directly in aqueous matrices. The use of the proper derivatizing reagent permits the production of organo-mercury compounds with different volatilities, but also toxicity, therefore the samples require cautious handling by the analyst both during the analysis and for the disposal. Recently, HS-SPME has been employed to quantify bivalent Hg and MeHg^+ using commercially available fibers. Specifically, freshwater samples were analyzed by a PDMS fiber (Fernández-Gómez et al., 2014), lake water with the PMDS/DVB coating (Zheng et al., 2018), and estuarine sediments using the three-phase fiber CAR/DVB/PDMS (Borowska and Jankowski, 2020). The target compounds, previously alkylated or photochemically reduced to Hg^0 , were identified through the effective combination of SPME with GC coupled to pyrolysis-atomic fluorescence spectrophotometry (Py-AFS) (Fernández-Gómez et al., 2014), MIP-OES (Borowska and Jankowski, 2020) or PD-OES (Zheng et al., 2018), thus developing simple and solventless methods with good environmental performance, that at the same time permitted the reaching of LODs significantly lower than those achieved using AES and AAS. Besides the use of commercial fibers, new coatings made with alternative materials or lab-made procedures have been proposed in Hg determination in order to improve the performance of the technique in terms of sensitivity, selectivity towards Hg species, and endurance. For instance, Vereda Alonso et al. proposed a silica MNPs

Table 1
Solid-phase based microextraction techniques for Hg determination in environmental samples.

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / sorbent phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) [†]	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺	Spring, river, and lake water	UA-d-μSPE / Fe ₃ O ₄ /g-C ₃ N ₄	CV-AFS	/	LOD: 1.4 ng/L LR: 0.005–0.4 μg/L	A: 90% P: 4.6%	(-) Reusability of magnetic sorbent; high throughput of the whole procedure (-) Competitive adsorption of coexistent ions	(Shi et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺	Drinking, tap, and surface water	d-μSPE or MDSPE / ODE@SiO ₂ @MNP	AAS	ODE	LOD: 4 ng/L LR: 0.05–5 μg/L	A: 90.1–99.0% P: 3.7%	(+) High selectivity (-) Time-consuming synthesis of the sorbent phase	(Khor et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺	Wastewater	d-μSPE / dendrimer-based nanomagnetic DF-MNS	CV-AAS	/	LOD: 0.03 μg/L LR: 0.08–6.0 μg/L	A: 90.0–106.7% P: 5.3%	(+) Easy and effective extraction from real matrices (-) Laborious preparation for the adsorbent material that is not reusable	(Ghodsi et al., 2021)
Hg ²⁺	Tap water, mineral water, wastewater, seawater, CRMs (lobster hepatopancreas, herring, cormorant, cod tissues)	d-μSPE / thiosemicarbazide-functionalized carbon nanotubes (CNT-TSC)	TXRF	/	LOD: 2.6 ng/L Linearity up to 100 μg/L	A: 99 – 103% P: 2.1%	(+) High adsorption capacity of the sorbent and high enrichment factor; use of a low power-consuming instrument (-) Time-consuming synthesis of the sorbent phase that is not reusable	(Musielak et al., 2021)
Hg ²⁺	Mineral water, well water, orange-spotted, grouper	d-μSPE / MGBG	UV-Vis	DZ	LOD: 2.11 μg/L; 63 ng/g LR: 7–100 μg/L; 210–3000 ng/g	A: 98–107% P: 2.39%	(+) Reusability of the sorbent phase; reduced analysis time; low instrument cost; user-friendly and accessible technique (-) Use of organic solvent; oxidation of magnetic components	(Faryadras et al., 2020)
Hg ²⁺	Ground water, mineral water	μSPE / activated carbon xerogel	UV-Vis	DZ	LOD: 7.8 μg/L LR: 30–280 μg/L	A: 95% P: 1.36%	(+) Reusability of the column; good precision compared to other techniques; small sample volume; low instrument cost (-) Off-line technique; high LOD compared to other techniques	(Carrera et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Spring water, tap water, ground water	USA d-μSPE /AgNPs	HR-CS ETAAS	/	LOD: 0.005 μg/L Linearity up to 20 μg/L	A: 96–104% P: 6–11%	(+) Lower cost of AgNPs compared to AuNPs (used in other studies); improved dispersion of the solid phase owing to the use of ultrasound; reduced analysis time (-) Not-reusability of the solid phase	(Krawczyk and Stanis, 2015)
Hg ²⁺ THg	Water pond, draw-well water, puddle water	d-μSPE / magnetic particles covered with functionalized AgNPs	ETAAS	/	LOD: 0.01 μg/L LR: 0.03–3.5 μg/L	A:96–103% P: 2.5–3.7%	(+) Speciation analysis without the use of a chromatographic technique; low amount of solid material (-) Loss of sensitivity in presence of other	(López-García et al., 2015)

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Table 1 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / sorbent phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) [†]	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
iHg MeHg ⁺ PhHg ⁺	Mineral, tap, and river water	μSPE / 3D graphene-Ni functionalized with IL	CV-AFS	Chloride ions from NaCl and HCl	LOD: 3.6 ng/L Linearity up to 8 μg/L	A: 97–105% P: 4.1%	ions at high concentrations (+) On-line separation and preconcentration system; speciation analysis without the use of a chromatographic technique; high stability of the microcolumn; no need for volatile organic solvent (-) Time-consuming synthesis of the solid phase	(Sotolongo et al., 2020)
Hg ²⁺	Fish	d-μSPE/ pectin/ Fe ₃ O ₄ /GO	ICP-OES	/	LOD: 0.11 μg/g LR: 0.39–14.98 μg/g	A: 88–101% P: 5.9%	(+) Determination of several toxic heavy metals; no need for derivatization reaction (-) Need for the synthesis of the sorbent that is not reusable	(Bozorgzadeh et al., 2021)
MeHg ⁺	Freshwater	HS-SPME / PDMS	GC-Py-AFS	3-mercaptopropyl functionalized silica gel embedded in a polyacrylamide	LOD: 5.8 pg LR: 29–1180 pg	A: 65% P: 4%	(+) Ability to discriminate between free MeHg ⁺ ions and MeHg ⁺ -DOM complexes (-) Need for derivatization reaction	(Fernández-Gómez et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	River water	HS-SPME / PDMS/ DVB	PD-OES	NaBEt ₄	LOD: 0.001 μg/L Linearity up to 20 μg/L	A: 90–130% P: 2.1%	(+) Solventless; simultaneous sampling, extraction, and preconcentration; low power consumption of the instrument (-) Need for derivatization; potential interference by high As and Sn concentration; high toxicity of the diethylmercury produced by derivatization	(Zheng et al., 2018)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	CRMs sediment	PCVG-HS-SPME / CAR/DVB/PDMS	MIP-OES	/	LOD: 15–22.5 ng/g LR: 0.5–10 μg/g	A: 87.3–101% P: 3.8–12.5%	(+) Speciation analysis; on-line system; small-scale instrumentation (-) Need for LLE for MeHg ⁺ extraction	(Borowska and Jankowski, 2020)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺	Surface water, wastewater	HS-SPME / homemade PDMS	GC-MS/MS	NaBPh ₄	LOD: 0.03–6 ng/L LR: Hg ²⁺ : 25.0–200 μg/L; MeHg ⁺ and EtHg ⁺ : 0.12–80.0 μg/L	A: 77–114% P: 3–12.1%	(+) Low-cost lab-made fiber; speciation analysis; solventless (-) Need for derivatization reaction; use of expensive instruments	(Li et al., 2020)
Hg ²⁺	Rainwater, river water, lake water	HS-SPME / carbonaceous nanoparticles	AFS and μPD-OES	NaBEt ₄	LOD: 0.0005 μg/L by AFS; 0.007 μg/L by μPD-OES LR: 0.5–10 μg/L	A: 84–107% by AFS; 79–115% by μPD-OES P: 5.8% by	(+) Simple and cost-effective synthesis of the fiber which is reusable; no use of chemicals; long-term preservation of	(He et al., 2020)

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Table 1 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / sorbent phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) [†]	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
THg	Seawater	FI-MSPME / DPTH-MNPs	CV-ETAAS	/	LOD: 7.8 ng/L LR: 10–50 µg/L	A: 97.0–107.0% P: 1.7%	AFS; 5.2% by µPD-OES ultratrace mercury on fiber (-) Need for derivatization reaction (+) Reusability of the sorbent phase; small sample volume; online system (-) Time-consuming synthesis of the coating; loss of MNPs	(Vereda Alonso et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Soil	SPME/IL	CV-AAS and UV-CV-AAS	/	LOD: 2.3 ng/g by CV-AAS; 5.14 ng/g by UV-CV-AAS LR: 0.029–3.4 µg/g	A: 97–100% P: 5% by CV-AAS; 7% by UV-CV-AAS	(+) Small sample volume; minimum matrix interferences (-) Not-reusability of the coating; need for matrix digestion with strong acids	(Stanisz et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	Tap, well, and river water, fish, shrimp	MR/IT-SPME / Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs	HPLC-DAD	DDTC	LOD: 0.035 µg/L; 4.2 ng/g LR: 0.50–150.0 µg/L; 25.0–15000 ng/g	A: 87–105% P: 2.6–5.4%	(+) Automated extraction and analysis (-) Need for derivatization; use of organic solvents	(Mei et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺ PhHg ⁺	Tap, river, and lake water, seawater	MFR/IT-SPME / Fe ₃ O ₄ doped task specific monolith	HPLC-DAD	DZ	LOD: 0.0067–0.016 µg/L LR: 0.05–300 µg/L	A: 81–117% P: 7.5%	(+) Online method for Hg speciation; small sample volume (-) Need for derivatization; use of organic solvents; need for EDTA to avoid the interference of co-existing ions	(Song et al., 2021)
THg	Tap, river, and bottled mineral water, rainwater	µSPE / GO functionalized with [C ₄ C ₁₂ im]Br	ETAAS	/	LOD: 14 ng/L Linearity up to 8 µg/L	A: 95.6–105% P: 3.9%	(+) Small sample volume; reusability of the microcolumn; high enhancement factor (-) Laborious synthesis of the sorbent; use of organic solvents	(Sotolongo et al., 2018)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Drinking and river water, seawater	dHS-ITEX / TA	GC-ICP-MS	NaBPr ₄	LOD: 0.08–0.4 ng/L	A: 95–136%	(+) Small amount of sample; Hg speciation; solventless (-) Need for derivatization; instrumentation expensive	(Hu et al., 2017)

[†] Concentrations in µg/L and ng/L refers to liquid matrices and ng/g and µg/g to solid matrices

CNT-TSC: thiosemicarbazide-functionalized carbon nanotubes

MGBG magnetic graphene-based bucky gel

AgNPs: silver nanoparticles

[C₄C₁₂im]Br: 1-butyl-3-dodecylimidazolium bromide

DDTC: sodium diethyldithiocarbamatetridrate C₅H₁₆NNaO₃S₂

DPTH-MNPs: 1,5-bis(di-2-pyridyl)methylene thiocarbohydrazide

DZ: dithizone

GO: graphene oxide

[Hmim][BF₄]: 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium tetra-fluoroborate

IL: ionic liquid

MNPs: magnetic nanoparticles

NaBEt₄: sodium tetraethylborate

NaBPr₄: sodium tetrapropylborate

ODE: 3-oxo-1,3-diphenylpropyl-2-(naphthalen-2-ylamino)-ethylcarbomodithioate

TA: tenax

Table 2
Liquid-phase based microextraction techniques for Hg determination in environmental samples.

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) [†]	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Freshwater fish, bottled mineral, river, and tap water	UA-DES-LPME / ChCl-phenol	ETAAS	DZ for Hg ²⁺	LOD: 0.073–0.091 µg/L; 0.0073–0.0091 µg/g LR: Hg ²⁺ : 0.1–10.0 µg/L; 0.01–1.0 µg/g MeHg ⁺ : 0.3–10.0 µg/L; 0.03–1.0 µg/g LOD: 0.15 µg/L; 0.24 ng/g LR: 0.5–100 µg/L; 0.8–160 ng/g	A: 81–115% P: 2.85–4.05%	(+) Small amount of sample; speciation analysis (-) Use of non-eco-friendly solvent; the need for derivatization	(Thongsaw et al., 2019c)
Hg ²⁺	Pine leaf, seawater, river fish, sand	DLLME / ethanol as disperser and chloroform as extractant	UV-Vis	DZ	LOD: 0.15 µg/L; 0.24 ng/g LR: 0.5–100 µg/L; 0.8–160 ng/g	A: 99–102% P: 3.6%	(+) Small sample volume; low instrumentation cost; short extraction time (-) Use of organic solvents as extraction and disperser	(Hossien-poor-Zaryabi et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	Tap, mineral, and river water, wastewater	DLLME, acetonitrile as disperser solvent and carbon tetrachloride as extraction solvent	UV-Vis	DZ	LOD: 2.6 µg/L LR: 10–300 µg/L	A: 94–104% P: 1.9%	(+) High enrichment factors; ease of operation; cheapness (-) Use of organic solvents as extraction and disperser	(Niazi et al., 2015)
THg	Wastewater, fish, river water, seawater	DLLME / methanol as disperser and carbon tetrachloride as extractant	CD-IMS	DEDTC	LOD: 10 µg/L; 100 ng/g LR: 35–10000 µg/L; 0.35–100 µg/g	A: 89–102% P: 3.4%	(+) Wide linear dynamic range; rapid separation and detection time (-) Use of organic solvents; lower sensitivity than other methods	(Jafari et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺	River water	DLLME / acetone as disperser and [C ₆ MIM][PF ₆] as extractant	HPLC-CV-AFS	2- ME	LOD: 1.5–3.0 ng/L LR: Hg ²⁺ : 5–450 ng/L MeHg ⁺ : 5–450 ng/L EtHg ⁺ : 10–1200 ng/L	A: 88–96% P: 5.1%	(+) Automated procedure; speciation analysis; low LOD (-) Use of acetone as disperser; the need for a chelating agent	(Liu et al., 2017)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺ PhHg ⁺	Tap and lake water, seawater	DLLME, ethanol as disperser and benzyl bromide as extractant	CE-UV	PAN and L-Cys	LOD: 0.23–1.79 µg/L LR: Hg ²⁺ : 5.0–200.0 µg/L MeHg ⁺ : 10.0–200.0 µg/L EtHg ⁺ : 10.0–200.0 µg/L PhHg ⁺ : 1.0–20.0 µg/L LOD: 0.04–0.1 ng/g LR: 0.5–50 ng/g	A: 82.4–98.8% P: 1.98–7.18%	(+) High selectivity and reliability for mercury speciation (-) Need for two chelating agents; use of benzyl bromide as extraction phase; need for back extraction process	(Yang et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	Fish	DLLME-SFO/1-undecanol as extractant; methanol as disperser	GFAAS	DDTP	LOD: 0.04–0.1 ng/g LR: 0.5–50 ng/g	A: 84–102% P: 3.5–6.2%	(+) Small volume of extractant; determination of several toxic heavy metals; short extraction time (-) Use of toxic organic solvent	(Pirsaheb and Fattahi, 2015)
Hg ²⁺	Freshwater fish, shrimp, and shellfish	ISLD-DLLME/1-octanol as extractant and methanol as disperser	HPLC-UV	PDC	LOD 100 ng/g LR: 250–10000 ng/g	A: 80–91% P: 3%	(+) High enrichment factor (230); short extraction time (-) Use toxic solvent organic; lack of automation	(Laosuwan et al., 2020)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	River, tap, and well	SPE-IP-SA-DLLME-SFO / CTAB as emulsifier	GFAAS	DDTP for extraction in	LOD: 0.009 µg/L;	A: 98–100% P: 4.8%	(+) Very high enrichment factor;	(Sadeghi et al., 2015)

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Table 2 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) ¹	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
	water, fish, tea leaves, pine leaf	and ion pairing and 1-undecanol as extractant		SPE and Γ^- for DLLME	4.5 ng/g LR: 0.02–20 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 0.01–10 $\mu\text{g/g}$		lower detection limit, applicability to multi-matrices (-) Need for two extraction methods; use of two chelating agents; use of organic solvent; laborious sample preparation	
Hg ²⁺	Wastewater, tap, bottled mineral, and river water	in-situ IL-DLLME / [Hmim][Cl]	SPCnAuEs	APDC	LOD: 0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ LR: 0.5–10 $\mu\text{g/L}$	A: 95–108% P: 13%	(+) The cheapness of analytical procedure (-) Laborious multi-step extraction procedure	(Fernández et al., 2015)
THg	Fish and shrimp	IL-ISFME 1-Hexyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate [Hmim][PF6]	CV-AAS	DZ	LOD: 0.08 $\mu\text{g/g}$ LR: 0.27–267 $\mu\text{g/g}$	A: 80–90.5% P: 4.8%	(+) Reusability of the sorbent; automated (-) Use of organic solvent; the need for a reducing reagent	(Molaei et al., 2017)
Hg ²⁺	Pond and tap water	TC-IL-DLLME / [OPy] ⁺ [BF ₄] ⁻	FD	/	LOD: 0.034 $\mu\text{g/L}$ LR: 0.1–0.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$	A: 80–110%	(+) No need for dispersive solvents; excellent selectivity for Hg ²⁺ (-) Use of organic solvent; extremely long analysis time	(Hui et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺	Pond, tap, and wastewater	TC-DLLME / N-octylpyridinium tetrafluoroborate ionic liquids	DPSV with gold disc electrode	/	LOD: 0.05 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Linearity up to 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$	A: 81–107% P: 10%	(+) Small sample volume, minimal space and power requirement; low instrumentation cost (-) Use of organic solvent; long equilibration time	(Li et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Plant (Dracaena sanderiana), drinking water	TSIL-DLLME the TSIL, [A336][TS] as extraction solvent	ICP-AES	/	LOD: 0.28 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 0.014 $\mu\text{g/g}$ LR: 1–5000 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 0.05–250 $\mu\text{g/g}$	A: 96% P: 1%	(+) Wide linear range; high tolerance to matrix interference (-) Laborious TSIL synthesis; use of organic solvents	(Sereshti et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	Fish, tap, river, and mineral water	SS-DLPME 1-octanol as extraction solvent	UV-Vis	TMK	LOD: 1.60 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 3.2 ng/g LR: 5–400 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 0.01–0.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$	A: 97–102% P: 1.6%	(+) High enrichment factor; low instrumentation cost; no need for dispersive solvent (-) Use of organic solvent; the need for derivatization; not automatable	(Hayati et al., 2021)
Hg ²⁺	Lake and tap water	D-DLLME / methanol and CCl ₄	GFAAS	PDC	LOD: 19 ng/L LR: 0.1–20 $\mu\text{g/L}$	A: 92–106% P: 3.4%	(+) High selectivity; reduced interference from coexisting heavy metal ions (-) Use of organic solvents; the need for two steps of DLLME	(Liang et al., 2015)
MeHg ⁺	CRM (fish muscle), river, lake, and tap water	D-DLLME / methanol and CCl ₄	GFAAS	DDTC	LOD: 13.6 ng/L; 0.23 ng/g LR: 0.05–10 $\mu\text{g/L}$; 0.83–167 ng/g	A: 99–104% P: 4.3%	(+) One step D-DLLME procedure; high selectivity; wide linear range (-) Use of methanol and CCl ₄	(Liang et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺	Sediment	ILs-VALLME / 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate	HPLC–CV-AFS	DZ	LOD: 0.032–0.042 ng/ g LR: Hg ²⁺ :	A: 88–97% P: 4.2–6.4%	(+) Speciation analysis; ease of operation; reduced extraction time	(Leng et al., 2015)

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Table 2 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) ¹	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺	Effluent, influent, lake, and river water	VA-LLME/ZnO-NF	CV-AFS	APDC	0.1–25 ng/g; MeHg ⁺ : 0.1–30 ng/g; EtHg ⁺ : 0.2–70 ng/g LOD: 0.019 µg/L LR: 0.1–10 µg/L	A: 89–106% P: 4.6%	(-) Need for derivatization (+) Short extraction time; low solvent; and sample consumption (-) Preparation of ZnO-NF	(Amde et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Tap and domestic water	VA-LLME/ TOABr-coated Au NPs	UV-Vis	/	LOD: 0.8 µg/L LR: 4.9–120 µg/L	A: 95–105% P: 4.7%	(+) No need for chelating agents; low-cost instrumentation (-) Use of organic solvent; is not automatable	(Martinis and Wuilloud, 2016)
MeHg ⁺ THg	Lake, well, and dam water, industrial wastewater, fish	NADES-UAME consisting of BtCl-sorbitol mixture (1:3)	UV-Vis	AzB	LOD: 0.25 µg/L; 1 µg/g LR: MeHg ⁺ : 0.7–340 µg/L; 2.8–1360 ng/g THg: 3–270 µg/L; 12–1080 ng/g	A: 92–98.7% P: 1.9–5.5%	(+) Short extraction time; high enhancement factor; low instrument cost; wide linear range (-) Need for DES synthesis; use of organic solvent	(Altunay et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺	Butterfish, fish river, and tap water	DES-USA- DLLME consisting of l-menthol and salicylic acid mixture (4:1)	ETAAS	DES was used as extractant and complexing agent	LOD: 0.34 µg/L 8.2 ng/g LR: 2–120 µg/L; 48–2880 ng/g	A: 90–100% P: 1.1–7.6%	(+) Very high enrichment factor (2400) (-) Time-consuming long synthesis of the sorbent; long extraction process; the need for two extraction techniques (MSPE and DLLME)	(Ragheb et al., 2021)
Hg ²⁺	Pond, well, dam, and mineral water	Ss-USA-LPME / 1-decanol in THF: water	UV-Vis	PAN	LOD: 2.6 µg/L LR: 8.3–1000 µg/L	A: 96–98% P: 2.4%	(+) Low instrument cost; wide linear range (-) Use of organic solvent; the need for a chelating agent	(Aydin et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Tap water, wastewater well, river, and bottled mineral water	SMS-UA-HLLME / 1-undecanol and Bu ₄ NOH	UV-Vis	Congo red solution	LOD: 0.33 µg/L LR: 1–450 µg/L	A: 96% P: 1.9%	(+) Simple instrumentation; fast extraction procedure; small volume of extracting phase (-) Not automatable; use of undecanol in the synthesis of SMS	(Altunay et al., 2021)
Hg ²⁺	Wastewater, tap, mineral, and river water, seawater	VA-SMS-LLME / 1-decanol/THF	UV-Vis	Quinalizarin	LOD: 0.3 µg /L LR: 1–100 µg /L	A: 95–98% P: 1.8%	(+) Very fast extraction step; ease of operation; cheapness (-) Use of organic solvent	(Gouda et al., 2020)
Hg ²⁺	surface soil, sandstone, claystone, coal	EW-LLME / DETA	CV-AAS	H ₂ DPC	LOD: 0.50 ng/L LR: 0.02–0.65 µg/L	A: 99% P: 4.8%	(+) Wide applicability to relatively complicated matrices; short extraction time (-) Use of organic solvent	(Ali et al., 2016)
Hg ²⁺	Seawater, dam water	SPS-LPME / protonated N,N-dimethyl cyclohexylamine carbonate–N,N-	UV-Vis	DZ	LOD: 0.19 µg/L LR: 10–300 µg/L	A: 95–105% P: 0.8%	(+) No need for advanced laboratory equipment (-) Need for EDTA to eliminate	(Khan and Soyhlak, 2016)

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Table 2 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) ¹	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	River, tap, and bottled mineral water, fish	dimethyl cyclohexylamine pair Hg ²⁺ : HF-(2)-LPME / toluene MeHg ⁺ : HF-(3)-LPME / toluene	ETAAS	DDTC for Hg ²⁺	LOD: 0.063–0.143 µg/L 0.16–0.36 µg/g LR: Hg ²⁺ : 0.5–7.5 µg/L; 1.2–19 µg/g MeHg ⁺ : 0.2–12.0 µg/L; 0.5–30 µg/g	A: 90% P: 2.3–3.6%	interference effects; need for a synthesis step of the SPS; use of organic solvent (+) Speciation analysis with no chromatographic system; high enrichment factor (-) Need for two extraction steps; use of several solvents involved in the extraction phase; the need for a masking agent such as EDTA at high concentrations of interfering ions	(Thongsaw et al., 2019a)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ EtHg ⁺ PhHg ⁺	Atmospheric particles, lake water, plant, sediment	HF-LLME/toluene	HPLC-ICP-MS	PAN	LOD: 4.1–5.6 ng/L; 1.02–1.4 ng/g LR: Hg ²⁺ : 0.02–5 µg/L; 5–1250 µg/g MeHg ⁺ : 0.01–5 µg/L; 2.5–1250 µg/g; EtHg ⁺ : 0.02–5 µg/L; 5–1250 µg/g; PhHg ⁺ : 0.02–5 µg/L; 5–1250 µg/g	P: 6–11%	(+) Small sample volume, high enrichment factor (-) Expensive and bulky instruments; use of organic solvent	(Chen et al., 2015)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺ PhHg ⁺	River and lake water, CRMs (dogfish muscle)	AD- HF-LLLME /chlorobenzene	LVSS-CE/UV	18-crown-6	LOD: 0.2–1.1 µg/L; 25–137 ng/g LR: Hg ²⁺ : 20–1000 µg/L; 2.5–125 µg/g MeHg ⁺ : 20–1000 µg/L; 2.5–125 µg/g PhHg ⁺ : 10–500 µg/L; 1–62.5 µg/g	A: 90–104% P: 3.8–8.1%	(+) Simultaneous extraction of organomercury and iHg species; reusability of HF; automated extraction; ease of operation; excellent enrichment factor (up to 2195) (-) Use of organic solvent; the need for a chelating agent	(Li et al., 2015)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Tap and river water, wastewater, sewage works effluent	HF-LPME, L-cys in the acceptor phase and ionic liquid membrane phase [C ₄ MIM][PF ₆]	HPLC-ICP-MS	DZ	LOD: 0.3–0.9 ng/L LR: Hg ²⁺ : 3 – 200 ng/L; MeHg ⁺ : 1–200 ng/L	A: 91–112% P: 2.1–3.5%	(+) Very high enrichment factor (1600); speciation analysis (-) Large sample volume; long extraction times	(Wang et al., 2015)
THg	River and tap water, fish	EME/ 1-octanol and 2% v/v DEHP	Microvolume UV-Vis	PAN	LOD: 0.7 µg/L; 12 ng/g LR: 2.3–950.0 µg/L; 40–9500 ng/g	A: 89–95% P: 5%	(+) High enrichment factor; no need for special equipment; short extraction time (-) Use of organic solvent; use of a derivatizing reagent for UV-Vis analysis	(Fashi et al., 2017)
Hg ²⁺	Tap and river water	EME/ 1-octanol and 2% v/v DEHP	SWASV	/	LOD: 0.01 µg/L LR: 2–10 µg/L	A: 89–97% P: 7.5–8.7%	(+) Short analysis time; low cost of analysis; ease of operation; not bulky instrumentation (-) Narrow linear dynamic range; use of organic solvent	(Kamyabi and Aghaei, 2016)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺		SFODME / undecanol	ETAAS	4-NOPD	LOD: 0.24 µg/L; 0.6 µg/g	A: 83–113% P: 2.0–4.4%	(+) Speciation analysis; no need for	(Sakanupongkul et al., 2019)

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Table 2 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) ¹	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺	Drinking, tap, and surface water, fish	SDME / undecanol	UV-Vis	DZ	LR: Hg ²⁺ : 0.83–8.0 µg/L; 2.1–20 µg/g MeHg ⁺ : 0.78–8.0 µg/L 1.9–20 µg/g LOD: 1.9 µg/L LR: 6.4–100.8 µg/L	A: 87–113% P: 8.5%	surfactant; ease of operation (-) Need for two SFO steps; not automatable (+) High enrichment factor; no need for expensive instrumentation; use of a small volume of extracting phase (-) Need for EDTA in the presence of other interfering ions; difficulty of separation of the two phases	(Pelit et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	seawater, wastewater, fish	LIS- HS-SDME / finely dispersed palladium microdrops	ETAAS	/	LOD: 0.48 µg/L; 4.2 ng/g LR: 1.6–40.0 µg/L; 14–350 ng/g	A: 96–98% P: 4.2%	(+) Automated; small sample volume; solventless (-) Narrow linear dynamic range; need for reducing agent	(Mitani et al., 2014)
Hg ²⁺	Lake and river water, wastewater	HS-SDME / TGA-AuNPs	UV-Vis	/	LOD: 0.2 µg/L LR: 0.2–2 µg/L	A: 87–100% P: 2.4%	(+) Low instrument cost; ease of operation (-) Narrow linear dynamic range; need for reducing agent; long extraction time	(Tolessa et al., 2018)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Pond and river water, sediment	CPE/PEG	UV-Vis	PAN	LOD: 5 µg/L LR: 10–100 µg/L	A: 94–105% P: 1–3%	(+) Small sample volume; inexpensive (-) Affected by the presence of some anions; need for a chelating agent	(Samaddar and Sen, 2016)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Wastewater	CPE / Triton X-114	HGAFS	KI and MG for Hg ²⁺ APDC for MeHg ⁺	LOD: 0.007–0.018 µg/L LR: 0.24–4.0 µg/L	A: 97–102% P: 3%	(+) Speciation analysis; No interference from the coexisting ions; non-chromatographic technique (-) Need for antifoam agent for eliminating the influence of surfactants; for speciation, a two-step CPE is required	(Zheng et al., 2019)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Fish	UA-CPE mixed surfactant of Tween 20 and SDS	UV-Vis	H ₂ TDC	LOD: 0.24–0.48 ng/g LR: Hg ²⁺ : 1.72–24.56 ng/g; MeHg ⁺ : 7–11.06 ng/g	A: 94–103% P: 2.8%	(+) High enrichment factor; speciation analysis; no need for expensive instrumentation (-) Use of toxic organic solvent; need for derivatization reaction	(Altunay, 2018)
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	Freshwater, bottled mineral water, river and tap water, fish	d-CPE / Triton X-114	ETAAS	DZ	LOD: 0.234 µg/L; 0.12 µg/g LR: 0.40–15.0 µg/L; 0.2–7.5 µg/g	A: 88–115% P: 4.8%	(+) Speciation analysis; low matrix effect (-) The extraction process involves	(Thongsaw et al., 2019b)

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Table 2 (continued)

Analyte	Matrix	Extraction method / liquid phase	Quantification technique	Derivatizing agent	LOD and Linear range (LR) [†]	Accuracy (A) and precision (P)	Pros (+) and cons (-)	Reference
Hg ²⁺ MeHg ⁺	River water, soil	d-CPE / Triton X-114	HPLC-HG-AFS	DDTC	LOD: 0.004–0.016 µg/ L; 0.032–0.128 ng/ g LR: 0.10–5.0 µg/ L; 0.8–40 ng/g	A: 85–110% P: 3.1%	several non-automatable steps (+) Speciation analysis; no significant interference from the common coexisting ions (-) Need for several manual steps	(Xie et al., 2021)

[†] Concentrations in µg/L and ng/L refers to liquid matrices and ng/g and µg/g to solid matrices

4-NOPD: 4-nitro-o-phenylenediamine

2-ME: 2-mercaptoethanol

[A336][TS]: tricaprilmethylammonium thiosalicylate

APDC: Ammonium Pyrrolidine Dithiocarbamate

AzB: 3-(dimethylamino)-7-(methylamino)phenothiazin-5-ium chloride

BtCl: Betaine hydrochloride

[C₆MIM][PF₆]: 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate

[C₄MIM][PF₆]: 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate

CCl₄: carbon tetrachloride

ChCl-phenol: phenol-choline

CTAB: cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide

DETA: diethylenetriamine

DEDTC: diethyldithiocarbamate

DDTC: diethyldithiocarbamate

DDTP: diethyldithiophosphoric acid

DZ: Dithizone

H₂DPC: 1, 5-diphenylcarbazone

[Hmim][Cl]: 1-hexyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride

KI: potassium-iodide

L-Cys: L-cysteine

MPS: 3-mercapto-1-propanesulfonic acid

[OPy]⁺[BF₄]⁻: N-octylpyridinium tetrafluoroborate

PAN: 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, PDC pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate,

PEG: polyethylene glycol

SDS Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate

TGA-AuNPs: thioglycolic functionalized gold nanoparticles

THF: tetrahydrofuran,

TMK: Thio-Michler's Ketone

TOABr: tetraoctylammonium bromide

Tween 20: polyoxyethylenesorbitan monolaurate

coating modified with 1,5-bis(di-2-pyridyl) methylene thiocarbohydrazide (DPTH-MNPs) for Hg²⁺ extraction in seawater. Using magnetic nanoparticles as SPME coating proved to be very effective in routine analysis for the determination of trace Hg because the online coupling with CV-AAS permitted reaching LOD of few ng/L with a small amount of sample (8 mL), and moreover the synthesized fiber turns out to be very robust ensuring at least 550 analyses (Vereda Alonso et al., 2016). A more recent alternative to commercial fibers was proposed by He et al. (He et al., 2020), who synthesized a coating of carbon nanoparticles by placing a stainless-steel wire in contact with a candle flame for 1 min (Fig. 1). The resulting fiber was used in HS-SPME and showed interesting performance in preserving the iHg collected up to nine days after sampling. This feature permitted in-situ Hg sampling from ambient waters, thus avoiding analyte loss during sample storage and transport due to adsorption on the inner walls of containers or degradation by photochemical/biochemical reduction of Hg²⁺ to Hg⁰ and subsequent volatilization. In addition, the ability to conduct HS-SPME in-situ enhanced the green nature of the method because the environmental costs of transporting heavy samples would be essentially avoided. Lab-made procedures were also employed to produce fiber coatings suitable for the quantification of speciated Hg, as was the PDMS fiber made by Li et al. exploiting sol-gel polymerization (Li et al., 2020). This fiber in HS

mode coupled with GC-MS/MS detection, was a viable and cost-effective alternative for the determination of MeHg⁺, EtHg⁺, and Hg²⁺, as it improved the LODs achieved by commercial fibers used in conjunction with GC-MS detection methods. A minus of this method was still the need to derivatize the organomercury compounds with sodium tetraethylborate (NaBET₄) and heat the sample to enrich the headspace for better sensitivity.

Ionic liquids (ILs) have also been proposed as SPME coatings for Hg determination. Although they have long been used for the extraction of organic compounds in various matrices (Xu et al., 2013; Yu et al., 2013), their application has been recently extended to the extraction of Hg²⁺ from industrial soils, using a task-specific ionic liquid-coated PTFE solid-phase microextraction tube (TSIL PTFE SPME) in direct immersion mode. A significant benefit of this configuration was that Hg was extracted through interaction with the coating without the need for potentially hazardous derivatizing agents. Besides, this extraction technique coupled with CV-AAS showed improved analytical performance compared to methods that exploit other extraction techniques coupled with spectrophotometric detection, while requiring a comparable sample volume (Stanisz et al., 2014).

Table 3
Key working principles of the discussed microextraction techniques.

	Technique	Key working principles
Solid-phase based microextraction techniques	μ -SPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The analyte sorption occurs eluting the sample on a sorbent packed inside a microcolumn. Desorption is performed by a reduced volume of a suitable solvent.
	SPME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the d-μSPE, the sorbent is dispersed in the liquid sample and the adsorption of the analyte is achieved by stirring or using ultrasound. Desorption depends on the type of sorbent material; in the case of phases with magnetic properties, the application of a magnetic field facilitates separation from the aqueous solution. In SPME, extraction occurs by partitioning the analyte between the sample and the extractive phase, which may be the coating on a fiber (in-fiber SPME) or the inner surface of an open tubular fused silica capillary column (IT-SPME). In-fiber SPME can occur by exposing the fiber to direct contact with the solution (DI-SPME) or to the vapor phase located above the sample (HS-SPME). The desorption step is carried out by thermal increase or by a minimal amount of solvent. In IT-SPME, the analyte trapped in the capillary column is desorbed using an appropriate solvent. The use of magnetic sorbents can improve the extraction efficiency of compounds with magnetic properties (MFR/IT-SPME or MR/IT-SPME).
	ITEX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The volatile analyte, or made volatile by derivatization, is partitioned into the headspace from which it is drawn several times through a syringe containing the sorbent phase. This is followed by the thermal desorption step of trapped molecules.
Liquid-phase based microextraction techniques	DLLME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The technique involves the use of three liquid phases: the aqueous samples, the immiscible extractant, and the dispersing solvent, which is soluble in both the sample and the extractant. These three phases are mixed, resulting in a cloudy solution, which is then centrifuged and the solvent, containing the extracted analytes, is finally collected. In IL-DLLME, ionic liquids are used as both the extracting and dispersing solvent. In TC-IL-DLLME, the temperature of the mixture can be varied to improve extraction efficiencies by varying the solubility of ILS. In D-DLLME displacement reactions predominantly promote the formation of the complex between the target metal and the ligand, avoiding the interference of other species.
	VA-LLME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A micro-volume of extraction solvent is dispersed into the sample solution and vortexed, producing small droplets useful to promote a rapid extraction of analytes due to the shorter diffusion distance and large surface area. The re-separation of the extractive phase is achieved by centrifuging the mixture before the instrumental analysis.
	DES-LPME and SMS-LPME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The operating procedure is similar to VA-LLME, so vortexing or ultrasound are used to promote emulsion between the two phases and simultaneously improve extraction efficiency, which is also enhanced by the properties of these two classes of solvents, DES and SMS.
	HF-LPME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The HF is immersed in an organic solvent, which impregnates the pores and thus produces a supporting liquid membrane (SLM). SLM thereby acts as a barrier between the sample and the acceptor phase, which has been previously added in the lumen of the HF. The HF is immersed in the sample and the analyte is transferred to the acceptor phase. When the extraction is complete, the acceptor solution is withdrawn and analyzed. If the acceptor phase is an aqueous solution it is referred to as HF-(3)-LPME, whereas if it is an organic solvent it is referred to as HF-(2)-LPME.
	EME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This technique is similar to HF-LPME; the difference relies on the use of an electric field, between a cathode inserted into the acceptor phase, and the anode in the sample, to accomplish the transfer of the charged analyte through the SLM. Agitation during extraction is used to enhance the migration of the charged analytes from the sample to the acceptor phase. Finally, the acceptor phase is withdrawn and analyzed.
	SDME and SFODME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In SDME, a reduced volume of extraction phase is added to the aqueous sample, which is suspended in the solution due to its lower density, with magnetic stirring enhancing the process. Then, the extraction phase is recovered using a syringe and analyzed. To easily recover the extractive phase, the solution can be immersed in an ice bath to achieve solidification of the extractive solution (SFODME). In HS-SDME, the extraction phase is placed in the headspace of the solution. In the case of Hg determination, extraction occurs following the addition of a reducing agent that converts the mercury species into Hg⁰.
	CPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sample and the extraction phase are mixed and heated up to the cloud point. The resulting cloudy solution is centrifuged and immersed in an ice bath to increase the viscosity of the extraction phase, thus promoting the separation from the aqueous phase. The d-CPE consists of two consecutive CPE processes in which the target analytes are back-extracted into the aqueous phase.

2.3. In-tube solid-phase microextraction and in-tube extraction

Similarly to the traditional in-fiber SPME, the in-tube solid-phase microextraction (IT-SPME), has often been used for the analysis of organic compounds (Prieto-Blanco et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018, 2014) and few applications concerned the determination of heavy metals, mainly due to a poor extraction efficiency that has limited its use (Mei et al., 2019). To overcome its drawbacks in this field of investigation, an evolution of the technique called magnetic-IT-SPME has been proposed, which relies on the magnetic microfluidic principle and the diamagnetism of the analytes. It has been demonstrated, in fact, that the use of a magnetic field can represent an alternative to focus or trap analytes as a function of their magnetic nature, i.e., diamagnetic compounds in a paramagnetic field concentrate in areas where the magnetic field is minimal (Moliner-Martínez et al., 2012). In 2019 Mei et al. developed a method for the quantification of iHg in well, river water, and fish samples using a monolithic capillary column consisting of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coupled online with an HPLC-DAD (Mei et al., 2019). The magnetic microfluidic approach, due to the application of the magnetic field, improved the extraction efficiency of metal ions during the adsorption phase but also their desorption for analysis, resulting to be a valid strategy for trace Hg determination in complex matrices. Given the

importance of the quantification of Hg species in environmental waters, the same research group has recently developed a new sorbent based on task-specific monolith doped with Fe₃O₄. This device was fabricated in situ within a capillary and used for the determination of properly chelated Hg species by magnetic field-reinforced in-tube solid-phase microextraction coupled online with HPLC-DAD (Song et al., 2021). This approach would be well suited for routine monitoring analysis as it showed excellent performance (LOD varied from 6.7 pg/L to 16 pg/L), automation, cost-effectiveness, low employment of sample.

To address some of the shortcomings of SPME, such as fiber fragility and limited extraction capacity, alternative microextraction techniques including in-tube extraction (ITEX) and solid-phase microextraction arrow (SPME-arrow) have been developed. So far the characteristics of the SPME-arrow have not yet been exploited in the Hg determination, while Hu and coworkers proposed for the first time the use of ITEX coupled with double isotope dilution GC-ICP/MS for MeHg⁺ and iHg speciation in river water, seawater, and drinking water (Hu et al., 2017). Analytes derivatized with sodium tetrapropylborate (NaBPr₄) were headspace extracted and trapped in the syringe needle body filled with Tenax TA, and finally thermally desorbed into the GC injector. This combination required the expensive and not very common coupling between GC and ICP, but resulted in low LODs (0.08 and 0.4 pg/g

Fig. 1. Procedural scheme of in situ synthesis of carbonaceous nanoparticles on the surface of stainless-steel fiber from a candle flame and subsequent Hg^{2+} determination: coating synthesis (a, b), analyte derivatization and HS-SPME extraction (c), analyte thermal desorption (d).

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MeHg^+ and iHg , respectively) and better extraction efficiency compared to those achievable with SPME. The whole procedure recalls the traditional purge-and-trap while providing better options in terms of automation and widespread application. Indeed, ITEX is a commercially available analytical solution, already used for the analysis of volatile organic compounds, and in coupling with gas chromatography is fully managed by the most modern autosamplers. This last feature is very important because it permits higher sample throughput using an instrumental setup not dedicated only to Hg determination, but also opens the way to future applications with high-resolution MS systems such as TOF and orbitrap.

3. Microextraction techniques based on liquid extraction phases

3.1. Dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction

Compared to the microextraction techniques based on the use of solid sorbents, the strategies based on the use of an extractive liquid phase (LPME) have played a major role in Hg determination in environmental matrices. Among these, dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME) has been widely used for sample preparation due to its great advantages such as simplicity, rapidity, cheapness, and environmental benignity. The combination of DLLME with simple instrumental detection techniques such as the UV-Vis spectrophotometry (Hossien-poor-Zaryabi et al., 2014; Niazi et al., 2015) has fostered the development of methods for Hg determination in environmental waters and plants with good reproducibility, high sensitivity, selectivity, and high enrichment factors. In 2016, DLLME was coupled for the first time with an ion mobility spectrometer equipped with a corona discharge ionization source (CD-IMS), thus combining the simplicity, affordability, and high enrichment factors of DLLME with the advanced sensitivity and detection speed of CD-IMS for the determination of THg in river water, seawater, and wastewater (Jafari et al., 2016). On the other hand, speciation analyses in aqueous and fish samples have also been possible using DLLME, through coupling with HPLC-CV-AFS (Liu et al., 2017),

CE-UV (Yang et al., 2014), and GFAAS (Sadeghi et al., 2015).

Numerous modifications of the traditional DLLME have been proposed to date, including the use of new extractive phases such as ionic liquids, which are organic molten salts with characteristics that generally make them environmentally friendly compounds, including reusability, thermal and chemical stability, non-inflammability and low volatility. Nevertheless, it is worth pointing out that not all ILs have a low environmental impact, in fact some include toxic ions and are not biodegradable (Kissoudi and Samanidou, 2018). ILs are relatively miscible with water and organic solvents, of which they are promising substitutes, especially for metal ion determination (Fischer et al., 2011) and therefore, in DLLME they can find application both as extraction and dispersion agents. Their synthesis can be carried out in-situ by exploiting a metathesis reaction between a precursor IL and an ion exchange salt, directly in the sample solution to be analyzed. In this regard, the most recent application of in-situ synthesized IL-DLLME for Hg determination in environmental waters was proposed in coupling with the use of screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with gold nanoparticles (SPCnAuEs) (Fernández et al., 2015). This synergistic combination represents an important intuition toward developing new inexpensive and portable methodologies for rapid measurements. An additional application of ILs in DLLME is by temperature control (TC-IL-DLLME), which has been coupled with a fluorescence detector (FD) (Hui et al., 2019) and differential pulse stripping voltammetry (DPSV) with a gold disc electrode (Li et al., 2016) for the Hg determination in pond, tap, and wastewater, achieving high enrichment factors, excellent selectivity, and low detection limits. Further improvements of ILs application in DLLME have been reached with task-specific ionic liquids (TSILs), which due to their higher specificity and their dual function as extracting phase and binding agent have been used for the selective extraction of Hg^{2+} in *Dracena sanderiana* plants and drinking water followed by quantification by ICP-AES, resulting in a sensitive method with a wide linear dynamic range (1–5000 $\mu\text{g/L}$), low solvent consumption (1 mL), and that compared to TC-IL-DLLME applications required shorter analysis times and a reduced sample volume (Sereshti et al., 2014).

A sticky point in the DLLME workflow is the recovery of the extraction solvent, which is a challenge due to the small volume involved. This issue has recently been addressed using narrow-diameter devices that, in the case of solvents with lower density than the aqueous solution, allowed for the rapid collection of the extractive phase before instrumental analysis. In this regard, for Hg determination, Laosuwan and co-workers employed a common plastic syringe for the in syringe low-density solvent-dispersive liquid microextraction (ISLD-DLLME) of iHg in fish samples, using octanol as the extractive phase, which was easily recovered into the tip of the syringe (Laosuwan et al., 2020), while Hayati et al. proposed a new technical strategy based on the use of a syringe-to-syringe system (SS-DLPME) using a UV-Vis detector for Hg determination in water, fish, and hair (Hayati et al., 2021). This latter analytical system, schematized in Fig. 2, entailed the connection of two syringes via a needle, thus obtaining a new configuration suitable as an extraction flask. The mixture of the liquid sample and organic solvent was passed from one syringe to the other several times until a cloudy mixture was formed. The small aliquot of the immiscible organic phase was then analyzed by adding distilled water to the mixture and thus forcing its surfacing into a capillary, from which it was easily sampled.

An alternative strategy for the collection of low-density extractive phases is the solidification by immersion of the solution in an ice bath (DLLME-SFO). In this way, the extraction solvent containing the analyte is easily separated and subsequently melted at room temperature before quantification. The combination of this technique with microwave-assisted extraction allowed to determine iHg and other heavy metals in fish samples by GFAAS (Pirsaheb and Fattahi, 2015). Nevertheless, compared to the aforementioned low-density solvent techniques, this strategy resulted to be less performing in terms of accuracy, enrichment factor, and because of the use of larger volumes of dispersant solvent.

The large number of studies with the use of DLLME is evidence of the applicability of this technique in Hg determination; nonetheless, some drawbacks are still present. Indeed, this strategy often relies on the formation of hydrophobic metal-chelating complexes that can be also the product of other metal ions present in the sample which may interfere competing in its formation. To tackle this issue, Yan and co-workers (Yan et al., 2002) developed a displacement/sorption pre-concentration protocol for the selective determination of metal ions in complex matrices based on the difference in stability of metal complexes. In this technique, displacement reactions promote the predominantly formation of the complex between the target metal and the ligand, avoiding interference from other species. Based on this strategy, Liang et al. have recently developed two methods for Hg quantification in river, tap, and lake water as well as in fish samples exploiting displacement dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (D-DLLME) coupled with GFAAS, using pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (Liang et al., 2015) and diethyl-dithiocarbamate (Liang et al., 2016) as chelating

agents. These methods minimized the interfering effects given by the presence of other metals without the need of masking agents, but also shown to be fast, simple, selective, sensitive, and therefore suitable for Hg determination in routine analysis of complex matrices. Another disadvantage of DLLME is the need to use a dispersion solvent that eventually decreases the partition coefficient of the analytes in the extractive phase. Furthermore, even if dispersing solvents are used in small amounts, they contribute to reducing the method greenness, especially when these solvents are hazardous such as chloroform (Hosien-poor-Zaryabi et al., 2014), carbon tetrachloride (Jafari et al., 2016; Niazi et al., 2015), and benzyl bromide (Yang et al., 2014). Alternatively, the dispersion of the solvent in the aqueous phase can be improved with the assistance of ultrasounds, though it can result in analyte degradation as a consequence of the high energies diffused through the analytical system (Sanchez-Prado et al., 2008). An attempt to overcome these drawbacks is the use of vortex-assisted liquid-liquid microextraction (VA-LLME), in which a micro-volume of solvent is dispersed into the aqueous sample using a vortex. The produced small droplets permit the rapid extraction of analytes because of the shorter diffusion distance and large surface area. The re-separation of the extractive phase is achieved by centrifuging the mixture before the instrumental analysis. In recent years, VA-LLME was used with tetraoctylammonium bromide coated AuNPs for the determination of iHg in tap and domestic water (Martinis and Wuilloud, 2016). The use of AuNPs in biphasic systems permitted the high extraction efficiency without the use of additional complexing reagents while the coupling with UV-Vis spectrophotometry made the method simple and with the environmental benefits also associated with the use of low running cost instrumentation (López-Lorente et al., 2022). Other applications of VA-LLME exploited the use of ILs as extractive phase (ILs-VA-LLME) in combination with chromatographic systems (HPLC-CV-AFS) for the determination of speciated Hg in sediments (Leng et al., 2015), as well as with spectrophotometric detection (CV-AFS) for the determination of iHg in aqueous samples (Amde et al., 2016). However, another shortcoming of VA-LLME and in general of DLLME is the difficulty in automating the protocols, e.g., due to steps such as centrifugation (Table 3). Improvements in this direction involving the determination of Hg were proposed by Molaei et al. who developed an automated system for the determination of THg in fishes and shrimp. This protocol entailed the in-situ formation of the IL used for the extraction and the phase separation carried out by a lab-made and reusable filter consisting of powder PTFE inserted into a medical syringe, in-line with a six-port valve (Molaei et al., 2017). On the same path, further advancement was made by Liu et al., who succeeded in automating the DLLME coupled with HPLC-CV-AFS for the Hg speciation in river waters (Liu et al., 2017).

In the wide range of applications of LPME, the use of deep eutectic solvents (DESS) for the quantification of organic and inorganic

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the SS-DLPME steps.

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compounds has recently gained increasing relevance (Shishov et al., 2017). However, although desirable due to their environmental benefits, their use in Hg determination has not yet found a wide application (Rastegarifard et al., 2017; Warrag et al., 2018). DESs are a subclass of ILs with a greater environmental friendliness combined with an easy and cost-effective synthesis. Their most recent use for iHg determination in fish and water samples involved a DES composed by a mixture of L-menthol and salicylic acid in a molar ratio of 4:1 that with the ETAAS detection resulted in very interesting enrichment factors (up to 2400-fold) at the detriment, though, of the sample throughput and the lack of automation (Ragheb et al., 2021). In the same field, another solution was the association of DES with ultrasound that, in two studies of Hg speciation in ambient water and fish samples, was exploited for its known ability in improving the mass transfer from aqueous solution to DESs as well as the formation of micellar aggregates promoting separation (Thongsaw et al., 2019c) (Altunay et al., 2019). The DESs proposed in these methods are particularly interesting from an ecological point of view because the components of the mixtures are molecules that can be also naturally available. These studies are indeed significant applications in Hg determination using natural DESs (NADESs), that in the coming years will be hopefully based on the exploitation of compounds easily extractable in large amounts from vegetables or industrial waste products.

A valid alternative to DES is currently offered by supramolecular solvents (SMS), which provide various types of interactions with metal-bonding complexes (dispersion force and hydrogen bonds), allowing for high extraction performance even in a short time, as was shown by the use of 1-decanol/THF as SMS for the iHg extraction in real water using ultrasound (Altunay et al., 2021; Aydin et al., 2016) or vortex stirring (Gouda et al., 2020).

The research of new solvents to be used in sample preparation is a trending research area, which has long been driven by the balance between improving extraction performance and the pursuit of sustainability. In this sense, an interesting solution is provided by switchable-polarity solvents (SPS), in which a reaction with CO₂ permits to change their chemical and physical properties, thus improving extraction efficiency (Anuwom et al., 2012). To date, however, their application for trace element determination is still very limited due to low sensitivity and the presence of matrix effect. Current applications for Hg determination included the use of diethylentiramine DETA as SPS (Ali et al., 2016) and the switching feature of the protonated N,N-dimethyl cyclohexylamine carbonate-N,N-dimethyl cyclohexylamine solvent pair (Khan and Soyjak, 2016).

3.2. Hollow fiber liquid-phase microextraction

Hollow fiber liquid-phase microextraction (HF-LPME) is an attractive technique for sample preparation as it permits the preconcentration and extraction of target analytes from also complex matrices ensuring high enrichment factors. HF-LPME requires only a few microliters of solvent for operation and can be classified according to the number of phases involved in the system: generally, two or three phases defined as HF(2)-LPME and HF(3)-LPME, respectively. In Fig. 3, the difference between these two approaches is illustrated, which essentially relates to features of the extractive solution contained in the hollow membrane lumen. In HF(3)-LPME (Fig. 3a) the acceptor is an aqueous phase, while in HF(2)-LPME (Fig. 3b) an organic phase is used (Carasek and Merib, 2015).

HF(2)-LPME has already been exploited for some years for the determination of organic and inorganic Hg in environmental waters (Chen et al., 2013; Xia et al., 2007), while the combined use of HF(3)-LPME and HF(2)-LPME has found a recent application in Hg speciation in fish, tap and river water (Thongsaw et al., 2019a). The analytical procedure entailed the extraction of MeHg⁺ by HF(3)-LPME using a toluene solution present within the pores of the hollow fiber and with thiosulfate as the acceptor phase, whereas iHg was isolated by

HF(2)-LPME upon complexation with diethyldithiocarbamate. The capabilities of HF(3)-LLME as a sample preparation technique were well exploited by Chen and co-workers who succeeded in developing a multi-matrix method for the speciation of iHg and organomercury compounds in the micro-ecosystem of East Lake (Wuhan, China) (Chen et al., 2015) that successfully dealt with atmospheric particles (PM), lake and river water, fish, plants, and sediments. The Hg species (organic and inorganic), after complexation with 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol, were simultaneously extracted with toluene and transferred into the aqueous solution of Na₂S₂O₃ inside the hollow fiber lumen and separated by HPLC-ICP-MS. Although difficult to implement, the development of analytical methods that simultaneously address several matrices is, for Hg determination, an outstanding feature because it complies with the requirement of Hg tracing in the environment also in accordance with recent international guidelines (UNEP, 2021).

Over the past few years, as for other microextraction techniques, some innovations to HF-LPME have been presented toward the improvement of automation and performance through the use of new materials. An instance was the study by Li and co-workers that designed a simple device for automatic dynamic hollow fiber-based liquid-liquid-liquid microextraction (AD-HF-LLLME) for the quantification of inorganic, methyl-, and phenyl- Hg in lake and river waters with improved analytical performance and high throughput (Li et al., 2015). On the other hand, in terms of materials, ILs have been used with success as the membrane solvents in the hollow fiber to replace compounds with higher environmental impact, such as toluene, 1-octanol, undecane, and cyclohexane. Excellent results in this respect have been achieved with an IL membrane containing a chelating agent (dithizone, DZ) immobilized in the pores of the hollow fiber, and the use of L-cysteine as the acceptor phase in the lumen (Wang et al., 2015). This sample preparation setup, combined with HPLC-ICP-MS instrumentation was used to quantify MeHg⁺ and iHg in tap, river, and waste waters with very good linearity, reproducibility, and high enrichment factors (above 1500-fold), owing to the barrier effect given by the ionic liquid membrane that counteracts the matrix effect, thus permitting Hg determination also in complex matrices. Nevertheless, the flip side of this approach is both the required extensive extraction times (about 720 min) and large sample volumes (about 400 mL) that would currently preclude its potential use for routine analysis (Wang et al., 2015).

Other satisfactory performances have been achieved with the electro membrane extraction (EME) in which, unlike HF-LPME, the extraction of the analytes did not occur through passive diffusion, but through the supported liquid membrane (SLM) with the application of an electrical field. The most recent EME applications to natural water analysis involved the coupling with a microvolume UV-Vis spectrophotometry, for THg determination (Fashi et al., 2017), and square wave anodic stripping voltammetry (SWASV) using a gold nanoparticle-modified glassy carbon electrode (AuNP/GCE) for Hg²⁺ determination (Kamyabi and Aghaei, 2016). In both methods, the extraction time was about 10 min and very good performances were also reached in terms of enrichment factors, sensitivity, and operating costs. The presence of the magnetic field was essential to have a marked reduction of extraction time with a potential increase in the sample throughput. Still to be explored is the use of EME for speciation analysis, potentially in combination with MS-based instrumental techniques to maximize the quantitative capability.

3.3. Single-drop microextraction and cloud point extraction

Single-drop microextraction, SDME, is a basic and well-known microextraction technique in which a micro-drop of an extraction solvent immiscible with the aqueous sample is exposed and then withdrawn for analysis (Table 3). Early applications involved the use of common hydrocarbon solvents as extractive phases, (e.g., cyclohexane, toluene, m-xylene, and n-octane), however, in an effort to use greener solutions, undecanol was recently proposed for the first time in SDME

Fig. 3. HF(3)-LPME e HF(2)-LPME.

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for the extraction of Hg derivatized with dithizone (Pelit et al., 2014). This method proved to be reliable even in complex matrices such as the saline ones that are rich in interferences, for which analysis can be challenging even using more sophisticated instruments. In addition, the miniaturization of the instrumentation coupled with a compact extraction system provides the method with the potential for in-field analysis, or for screening analysis of environmental samples given the high speed of analysis (about 6 samples in less than 30 min). Similar to the better-known SPME, SDME can also be employed in headspace mode (HS-SDME), where the micro-drop is used to extract volatile and semi-volatile analytes. For Hg determination, the most recent methods involved the reduction of Hg^{2+} to the volatile Hg^0 , which was then extracted with an aqueous micro-drop consisting of finely dispersed palladium (Mitani et al., 2014), or micro-drop of thioglycolic acid-functionalized gold nanoparticles (TGA-AuNPs) (Tolessa et al., 2018) and subsequently analyzed by ETAAS and UV-Vis spectrophotometry, respectively.

A change in the basic operating principle of SDME was made with solidified floating organic drop microextraction (SFODME), first proposed in 2007 (Khalili Zanjani et al., 2007). The novelty of this approach lies in the use of a few microliters of an extracting solvent with a melting point close to room temperature (10–30 °C). After extraction, it is solidified by lowering the sample temperature and then easily separated from the aqueous phase to be redissolved and analyzed (Table 3). This technique has been proposed for the determination of various heavy metals (Rivas et al., 2010; Yamini et al., 2010) including MeHg^+ and iHg in water and fish samples using 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine to chelate Hg^{2+} and undecanol as extraction solvent (Sakanupongkul et al., 2019). These methods did not include analysis speed among their strong points because the freezing and melting steps extend the sample preparation. However, looking at the figures of merit, SFODME permitted to reach good results in terms of precision and accuracy, proving to be particularly suitable in future implementation for Hg speciation in environmental matrices, but also food and clinical applications. Given the specific features and the potential implementation of non-toxic solvents for the extraction, SDME techniques have a good propensity to be used in methods with low environmental impact, also when compared to LLME approaches. To date, there has been no application with DESs for

the determination of Hg; besides, the reduced volume of extraction solvent would make the SDME a potentially exploitable technique also in combination with direct Hg analyzers based on thermal desorption. Indeed, this analytical equipment is already prescribed in official methods (e.g., USEPA Method 7473), but the use in combination with SDME has not yet been explored.

Another interesting microextraction approach, that is alternative to the SDME or LLME previously discussed, is the cloud point extraction (CPE) which exploits the turbidity phenomenon of surfactants in aqueous solution when heated at the cloud point temperature (Table 3). This technique has found recent use in the Hg speciation in environmental water and sediment using UV-Vis as detection techniques (Samaddar and Sen, 2016) or atomic fluorescence spectrophotometry with a hydride generator (HG-AFS) (Zheng et al., 2019). Although the proposed methods had several advantages such as the effective separation of Hg^{2+} and MeHg^+ with no need for chromatographic techniques, the use of CPE may potentially be limited by the high viscosity of the surfactant-rich phase that can be of concern for instrumental injection systems. This drawback is usually addressed by diluting this phase with the unavoidable decrease of the enrichment factor, or it can be tackled by using the dual cloud point extraction (d-CPE)-CPE, in which the analytes extracted into the surfactant-rich phase are back-extracted with an acidic aqueous solution. As observed for the determination of MeHg^+ and iHg in sediment, fish, drinking and river waters, this strategy led to improved efficiency and selectivity because the acidic solution containing the enriched metals is more compatible with instrumental techniques such as atomic absorption spectroscopy (Thongsaw et al., 2019b) and HPLC-HG-AFS (Xie et al., 2021). With d-CPE, the analyst ends up extending the experimental workflow by an additional step, this results in additional waste products and a more laborious procedure, which constitute adverse points in the evaluation of the eco-friendliness of sample preparation (López-Lorente et al., 2022).

4. Concluding remarks and future directions

Hg is one of the priority pollutants at a global level, and the scientific community is making increasing efforts for its control. Nowadays, it is the target of international monitoring networks in support of the

objectives of the MCM, but also the focus of major earth observation and metrology research programs. In this framework, our review aimed to show the recent developments made by microextraction techniques in the determination of Hg in environmental matrices. Despite the ubiquitous nature of Hg and the wide variety of matrices within the natural compartments, most of the developed methods using microextraction techniques focused on the determination of total and/or speciated Hg in aqueous matrices (e.g., lake, river, wastewater, pond water), while in solid matrices the applications still have great untapped potential.

In the Hg determination, microextraction techniques present analytical solutions with a low environmental impact that point toward the sustainability and environmental friendliness outlined in the principles of the green analytical chemistry (GAC) and the most recent green sample preparation (GSP) guidelines (López-Lorente et al., 2022; Sajid and Plotka-Wasyłka, 2022). The progress of research has seen the emergence of new techniques as well as the improvement of those already exploited in other analytical contexts, with introducing new procedures and materials. These latter have played a key role in permitting significant advances to microextraction techniques in terms of sensitivity and selectivity in complex matrices. Still to be explored is the use of sustainable natural or recycled materials as an extractive phase, an interesting direction of innovation already undertaken by microextraction techniques for other analytical targets (Mafra et al., 2019).

Over the years, there has also been a marked increase in the presentation of approaches that have been defined as new with an association of the relative acronym. In our opinion, this tendency is, in some cases, pretentious considering that often these are actually implementations or variations, which albeit important, would not be sufficient to be defined as pioneers of a new strategy. Although many microextraction techniques have already been evaluated, other important approaches such as cold-fiber SPME, vacuum-assisted HS-SPME, and arrow-SPME have not yet found application in Hg determination. This fact is particularly interesting considering that arrow-SPME is a commercially available solventless technique and its features would make the methods more easily implementable for extensive Hg monitoring.

A significant contribution to the sustainability and simplicity of Hg monitoring would be provided by implementing methods for in-situ analysis or that allow for sample preparation in the field. Despite the quantification in the field is a direct attribute of sensor systems, the use of an in-situ lightweight and space-saving microextraction techniques could make sample preparation easier and would help to lower the cost of sample transport to the laboratory, with the related reduction of the carbon footprint. These advantages are particularly interesting when considering that Hg needs to be globally monitored and that in most cases observatory stations are only concerned with sampling, while the analyses are carried out in a few specialized centers. In this sense, there are still few research papers designed for in-situ operation, partly due to clear technical limitations. At the same time, we are persuaded that this lack is also due to the not complete awareness that bringing sample preparation to the field is an important research aim that should instead guide scientific decisions.

An equally important gap is in using microextraction techniques associated with passive sampling. Indeed, although air has been a key matrix investigated for decades for the verification of global Hg levels, the poor extraction performance of solid microextraction sorbents has not yet allowed extensive exploitation in this sampling mode. Using passive sampling, already applied with other sampling devices, permits to greatly improve the greenness of a method but it is also strategic to obtain information on Hg levels in remote areas poorly accessible with traditional measurement systems that exploit active sampling. Interesting solutions in this sense would come from the use of microextraction techniques with large contact surface area as the thin-film SPME and fabric phase sorptive extraction, which adapted in materials would bode well for potential future implementations in Hg

quantification.

A close analysis of quantitative performance shows that most of the discussed methods meet the threshold values specified by the legislators. Nevertheless, there are about 20 protocols left out where sample preparation was addressed mostly with DLLME which, due to their inadequate performance, could not find a real application in the assessment of Hg exposure levels. Method development required the careful evaluation of numerous analytical parameters, which have rarely been evaluated in a multivariate mode. This point seems to be outweighed by the importance of the technique itself and its novelty, but in practice when optimization is carried out without the use of experimental design techniques (DoE), there remain many questions about the actual performance that a method could achieve if optimum working conditions were explored. From this, we infer that many of the methods discussed could possibly perform better than what is presented and therefore we hope that in the future the DoE will be systematically used to support the definition of new protocols. It is worth mentioning that in order to use the "right tool for the right job", the study of the analytical system with DoE response surface methodologies allows the analyst to have a deep understanding of the performance of the technique over the entire experimental domain. This in-depth evaluation permits a conscious choice of the working conditions following the analyst's aim, which can be the maximization of the figures of merit or the reduction of the environmental cost (López-Lorente et al., 2022).

The Hg determination was carried out mainly using spectrophotometric analytical techniques and, to a lesser extent, with more expensive technologies such as those based on mass spectrometry. This was made possible by the capabilities of microextraction techniques in sample-prep that effectively overcome problems due to interferences, especially with complex matrices. Nevertheless, although the opportunity to use low-cost instrumentation is an additional advantage in environmental matters, it would be of certain interest to expand the coupling of microextraction techniques with those of high-resolution mass spectrometry (e.g., orbitrap and TOF), also in ambient-MS mode.

It is worthwhile to conclude this discussion by drawing attention to the quality of the proposed analytical methods. Validation is a fundamental step in the workflow that leads to the creation of a new method, but it is often not addressed with enough rigor. More generally, from the discussion of the studies, it was clear the urgency of greater metrological support in the definition of new future analytical strategies for Hg quantification, which are robust, reliable, and traceable, thus improving the comparability of results. In fact, in most cases certified matrices were not used, some figures of merit were not investigated, or as often happens for LOD and LOQ, were evaluated following different indications, which even if legitimate, make it hard to compare the performance achieved. In our opinion, a valid way of comparison (although not comprehensive) is the linear dynamic range, which for this reason was used in the discussion of the work.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Domenico Amico: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Antonella Tassone:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Nicola Pirrone:** Funding acquisition. **Francesca Sprovieri:** Funding acquisition. **Attilio Naccarato:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The Authors would like to acknowledge the contribution received from the following projects:

- FET Proactive project "Towards new frontiers for distributed environmental monitoring based on an ecosystem of plant seed-like soft robots" (I-Seed). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017940.
- EU-H2020 project "EuroGEO Showcases: Applications Powered by Europe" (e-shape) (Grant Agreement: 820852), funded under H2020-SC5-2018-2 "Strengthening the benefits for Europe of the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) - establishing EuroGEO".
- EMPIR - EURAMET project "Metrology for traceable protocols for elemental and oxidised mercury concentrations" (SI-Hg); grant no. 19NRM03. This project (SI-Hg) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

This article is based upon work conducted by members of the Sample Preparation Study Group and Network of which Dr. Attilio Naccarato is a participant, and thusly supported by the Division of Analytical Chemistry of the European Chemical Society.

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